

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES
SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

NEUROLOGICAL PRESENTATION IN CHILDREN WITH SICKLE CELL DISEASE OF ARAB INDIAN HAPLOTYPE

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Abstract:

Background: Neurological complications are among the most disabling outcomes in children with sickle cell disease (SCD). Although SCD is highly prevalent in Saudi Arabia, data on neurological involvement among children with the Arab-Indian haplotype remain limited. This study aimed to describe the spectrum of neurological manifestations and identify modifiable risk factors associated with clinical outcomes.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study of 944 children (<14 years) with SCD was conducted between 2015 and 2022 at Qatif Central Hospital and Prince Mohammed bin Fahad Hospital. Only patients with neurological symptoms or abnormal neuroimaging were included (n=40). Clinical features, laboratory results, imaging findings, and outcomes were analyzed.

Results: Headache (55%), stroke (25%), and convulsions (12.5%) were the most common neurological manifestations. MRI abnormalities included ischemic stroke (12.5%) and moyamoya disease (7.5%). Exchange transfusion significantly improved outcomes in high-risk stroke patients (P=0.026). In contrast, patients with moyamoya disease showed no significant improvement with treatment (P=0.054). Higher Hemoglobin-F levels were associated with favorable outcomes (P<0.05). Patients with early-onset symptoms had poorer prognosis.

Conclusion: Neurological complications remain a major concern in children with SCD even with early diagnosis and hydroxyurea therapy. Early neuroimaging, prompt identification of high-risk patients, and timely initiation of exchange transfusion can significantly improve outcomes. Systematic monitoring for cognitive and cerebrovascular changes is essential to prevent long-term disability.

Keywords: sickle cell disease, neurology, pediatric, stroke, Arab-Indian haplotype

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Please cite this article in press Zahra Hussein et al., Neurological Presentation In Children With Sickle Cell Disease Of Arab Indian Haplotype, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(11).

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT:

A flow diagram illustrating:

- 944 total patients → 40 with neurological symptoms
- Most common symptoms: Headache → Stroke → Seizures
- MRI findings: Ischemic stroke, Moyamoya, PVL
- Key modifier: High HbF → Better outcomes
- Intervention: Exchange transfusion → Reduced stroke recurrence
- Poor outcome factors: Early symptom onset, Abnormal EEG, Low BMI

Key Points

- Neurological complications remain a significant cause of morbidity in children with SCD despite early diagnosis and hydroxyurea use.
- Headache, stroke, and seizures were the most common neurological presentations in this cohort.
- Higher Hemoglobin-F levels were associated with more favorable neurological outcomes.
- Exchange transfusion significantly reduced stroke recurrence and improved clinical status among high-risk patients.
- Moyamoya disease showed limited response to current treatment strategies, indicating the need for earlier detection and specialized vascular management.
- Early identification, regular neuroimaging, and targeted preventive strategies are essential to reduce long-term neurological disability.

INTRODUCTION:

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is one of the most common severe monogenic disorders affecting millions of patients worldwide, and approximately 300,000 new cases are reported annually.¹ It is characterized by the inheritance of two abnormal hemoglobin (beta globin) genes. It is a chronic hemolytic anemia characterized by red blood cells primarily containing hemoglobin S (HGS), which polymerizes when deoxygenated. When HGS is polymerized, the affected red blood cells become rigid and may block small blood vessels, causing platelet adherence and fibrin deposition. This cascade is repeated until the vessel becomes severely narrowed, causing cerebrovascular disease.² SCD can cause severe pain, significant end-organ damage, pulmonary complications, and premature death.

Neurological manifestations are a major concern in children with SCD. These manifestations range from mild cognitive deficits to severe stroke, which can profoundly impact a child's development and quality of life. Stroke affects approximately 10% of children with SCD (HbSS).³ While the precise mechanisms triggering these complications are not yet fully understood, the multifactorial nature of SCD likely contributes to their development. Several strategies have been employed to prevent and manage these complications, including regular screening for cognitive deficits, prophylactic blood transfusions, and hydroxyurea therapy. Additionally, early identification and treatment of acute neurological events, such as stroke, are crucial to minimize the long-term effects of these complications.

Children with SCD who suffer from stroke face a high risk of recurrent strokes up to 66% without secondary prevention. Chronic transfusion therapy significantly reduces this risk and is the current

standard of care for secondary stroke prevention. However, this approach carries long-term complications such as iron overload and alloimmunization. Transitioning selected patients to hydroxyurea after a stable period of transfusion therapy has been investigated as a safer long-term alternative. Neurocognitive impairment is also common following stroke in SCD and can affect academic achievement and social functioning. Therefore, comprehensive management often includes neuropsychological assessments and educational support. Emerging therapies and individualized risk stratification approaches are being explored to improve outcomes and reduce the treatment burden.

We aimed to investigate the range of neurological manifestations in children with SCD and identify the modifiable risk factors specific to this population.

METHODS

This retrospective descriptive cohort study was conducted for 7 years between 2015 and 2022 at Qatif Health Network (including Qatif Central Hospital and Prince Mohammed bin Fahad Hospital), Eastern Province, Saudi Arabia. The cohort included 944 children aged >1 year and <14 years (boys and girls) who were following up at the hematology clinic. The main data sources were patients' medical records from patient charts and the hospital's electronic medical system. Furthermore, patient demographic, clinical course, and clinical outcome data were collected. Patients with no neurological symptoms were excluded, and those with symptoms or investigations suggesting neurological involvement were included in this study.

This study was approved by the Medical Research and Ethics Committee of Qatif Health Network (approval number: QCH-SREC0 20/2022). The study was conducted in accordance with good clinical practice guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Statistical Analyses

Descriptive analysis and hypothesis testing were performed using SPSS v26. Categorical data were summarized using frequencies and percentages, whereas continuous data were summarized using means and standard deviations.

For Bivariate analysis, Pearson's chi-square test was used for categorical predictor variables, and an independent t test was used for continuous predictor variables. P values of <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Study Population

The total sample included 944 patients with SCD who were followed up at the Qatif Health Network. Of these, 904 patients were excluded because they had no neurological symptoms. Forty patients (13 female [32.5%] and 27 male [67.5%] individuals) were included in the study because their symptoms or findings suggested neurological involvement. The age at which the neurological symptoms developed varied between 8 and 14 years, with a mean age of 11 years.

Patients were divided into two groups: favorable and unfavorable outcomes. A favorable outcome was defined as the absence of long-term neurological deficits, full recovery from the neurological event, and preserved quality of life without permanent disability. In contrast, an unfavorable outcome was defined as the persistence of neurological deficits, development of permanent neurological damage (e.g., cognitive impairment, motor weakness, sensorineural hearing loss), or a significant negative impact on the patient's quality of life (Figure 1).

Fig. 1

FIGURE CAPTION

Fig. 1 Study flow diagram

Forty (13 female [32.5%] and 27 male [67.5%] individuals) of the 944 patients with sickle cell disease (SCD) who were followed up at Qatif Central Hospital and Prince Mohammed bin Fahad Hospital had neurological presentation. Twenty-seven patients [67.5%] had favourable outcomes and 13 female [32.5%] had unfavourable outcomes.

Figure Citation

Figure 1: Study flow diagram. Source: Hussein, Z. J., Aldarwish, M., Aljulaih, H., Alsultan, M., & Almubarak, S. (2023). Neurological Presentation in Children with Sickle Cell Disease of Arab Indian Haplotype.

Table 1:

Summary of Neurological Characteristics, Imaging Findings, and Outcomes in Pediatric SCD Patients (N = 40)

Category	Variable	n	%
Presenting CNS Symptoms	Headache	23	57.5%
	Convulsion	7	17.5%
	Weakness	5	12.5%
	Dizziness	3	7.5%
	Phonophobia	2	5.0%
	Hallucination	2	5.0%
	Other (photophobia, aphasia, sudden vision loss)	3	7.5%
	CT Brain Findings	Normal	25
Not done		10	25.0%
Ischemic stroke		2	5.0%
Brain hematoma		1	2.5%
Periventricular leukomalacia		1	2.5%
MRI Brain Findings		Normal	26
	Not done	2	5.0%
	Ischemic stroke	5	12.5%
	Moyamoya disease	3	7.5%
	Periventricular leukomalacia	2	5.0%
	Other (IIH, brain volume loss, CPA arachnoid cyst)	3	7.5%
Final Neurological Diagnoses	Headache	22	55.0%
	Stroke	10	25.0%
	Convulsion	5	12.5%
	Moyamoya disease	3	7.5%
	Hallucination	2	5.0%
	Vertigo	1	2.5%
	Photo/Phonophobia	1	2.5%
	Sudden loss of vision	1	2.5%
	Bilateral SNHL	1	2.5%
	Encephalopathy	1	2.5%
Outcome & Risk Factors	Improved on exchange transfusion	—	P=0.026
	Moyamoya not significantly improved	—	P=0.054
	EEG linked to unfavorable outcome	—	OR=14.67, P=0.037

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Table 2

SCD with high HGB F outcome crosstabulation:

	Favourable outcome	percentage	Unfavourable outcome	percentage	Total	percentage
SCD with High HGB F	20	50.0%	6	15.0%	26	65.0%
SCD with No High HGB F	7	17.5%	7	17.5%	14	35.0%
Total	27	67.5%	13	32.5%	40	100%

TABLE CAPTION

Table 2: SCD with high HGB F Crosstabulation of Outcome

Relationship between Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) with High Haemoglobin F (HGB F) and Favorable/Unfavorable* Outcomes (n=40)

Table Citation

Table 2: SCD with high HGB F Crosstabulation of Outcome. Source: Hussein, Z. J., Aldarwish, M., Aljulaih, H., Alsultan, M., & Almubarak, S. (2023). Neurological Presentation in Children with Sickle Cell Disease of Arab Indian Haplotype.

Diagnosis

SCD was diagnosed between the ages of 1 and 2 years due to the primary health care screening program during vaccination; therefore, there was no delay in diagnosis in our population. All 40 patients had SCD. One patient (2.5%) had bronchial asthma and another (2.5%) had birth asphyxia as comorbidities.

Neurological Features

The following central nervous system (CNS) symptoms occurred among the patients: headache (57.5%), convulsion (17.5%), weakness (12.5%), dizziness (7.5%), phonophobia (5%), and hallucination (5%). Furthermore, 7.5% of the patients presented with other features, including photophobia, aphasia, and sudden loss of vision, each accounting for 2.5%.

Radiographic imaging was performed on the patients. The initial screening tool is Computed tomography (CT) brain and revealed that 62.5% of the patients were normal, 25% did not undergo CT, 5% had ischemic stroke, 2.5% had brain hematoma, and 2.5% had periventricular leukomalacia.

For more details assessment, Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was performed and it showed normal results in 65% of the patients, whereas 5% of the patients did not undergo MRI. MRI revealed that 12.5% of the patients had ischemic stroke, 7.5% had moyamoya disease, and 5% had periventricular leukomalacia. In addition, 7.5% were categorized as "others," including idiopathic intracranial hypertension, mild brain volume loss, and cerebellopontine angle arachnoid cysts, each accounting for 2.5%.

The neurological manifestations observed in the patients included headache (55%), stroke (25%),

convulsion (12.5%), moyamoya disease (7.5%), hallucination (5%), vertigo (2.5%), photo and phonophobia (2.5%), sudden loss of vision (2.5%), bilateral sensorineural hearing loss (2.5%), and encephalopathy (2.5%). Patients who had a higher risk of stroke, defined by abnormal transcranial Doppler (TCD) velocities (>200 cm/s), history of previous stroke, or presence of silent cerebral infarcts on MRI, and were started on exchange blood transfusion showed significant improvement in terms of reduced stroke recurrence and stabilization or resolution of neurological symptoms ($P=0.026$), whereas those who had moyamoya disease did not show significant improvement in terms of neurological feature resolution or stabilization of cerebrovascular findings on imaging ($P=0.054$).

Patients who underwent electroencephalography had 14.67 times higher odds of experiencing an unfavorable outcome. This association is likely because these patients presented with more severe symptoms ($P=0.037$), (Table 1).

Laboratory Findings and Final Diagnosis

We correlated the laboratory results with the patients' final diagnosis and found that patients with higher hemoglobin F were less likely to have stroke ($P=0.018$) and moyamoya disease ($P=0.037$) (Table 2), in contrast to those with a high HGS level. Patients with a higher HGS level had a significantly higher incidence rate of moyamoya disease ($P=0.004$).

Treatment and Outcome

Thirty-three patients (82.5%) received hydroxyurea, three (7.5%) received a blood transfusion, two (5%) received an exchange blood transfusion, one (2.5%) received intravenous immunoglobulin, and six (15%) received no treatment.

Thirty-eight patients (95%) were regularly followed up, whereas two were followed up irregularly. Other diseases associated with SCD in our patients included painful vaso-occlusive crisis (20%), acute chest syndrome (15%), pulmonary embolism (2.5%), and hemolytic anemia (2.5%).

Patients who developed CNS symptoms early (mean age: 6.85 years) had unfavorable outcomes, whereas patients who had favorable outcomes experienced symptom onset at a mean age of 9.78 years.

The study's findings show that patients with unfavorable outcomes defined as persistent neurological deficits, recurrent stroke, or progressive cerebrovascular disease on imaging had a lower body mass index (mean: 14.6 kg/m²) than patients with favorable outcomes (mean: 16.87 kg/m²).

DISCUSSION

In Saudi Arabia, SCD was first reported in the eastern province in the 1960s.⁴ Most people with SCD in Saudi Arabia live in the eastern and southwestern provinces. However, the disorder follows a more severe clinical course among patients in the southwestern province than those in the eastern province, as the southwestern population carries African-derived haplotypes, whereas most of the eastern population carries the Arab-Indian-globin gene-like cluster haplotype.⁵ In the United States, more than 230,000 hospital admissions related to SCD occur annually at an economic cost of \$2.4 billion.⁶

In SCD, recurrent episodes of vaso-occlusion or inflammation can result in progressive damage to most organs, including the brain, kidneys, lungs, bones, and the cardiovascular system, which becomes apparent with increasing age.⁷ Potential brain complications of SCD in children, such as the development of cerebrovascular disease and cognitive impairment, have been reported.

The long-term outcome of SCD is associated with significant comorbidities and a shortened lifespan in children and adults in low-resource settings and adults in high-resource settings. In high-resource settings, at least 98% of children with SCD are now expected to reach adulthood^{8,9} owing to improved medical care, parents' anticipatory guidance regarding medical complications, conjugated vaccines for previously life-threatening infections, penicillin prophylaxis, blood transfusion and hydroxyurea for the prevention of potential complications. However, the next immediate challenge in the medical care of children with SCD in high-resource settings is preventing end-organ dysfunction, particularly of the brain. However, improving childhood survival and preventing end-

organ dysfunction are pressing needs for children in low-resource settings.

Regardless of the setting, children with SCD experience several neurological complications, including seizures, headaches, neurocognitive impairment, silent cerebral infarcts, and ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes. The median onset age of an initial ischemic stroke in an unselected population of children with SCD who were not screened for abnormal transcranial Doppler (TCD) was 6 years, with a prevalence of approximately 11% by 18 years of age.¹⁰ The risk factors for ischemic stroke in children with SCD include low hemoglobin oxygen saturation, the presence of silent strokes, and abnormal TCD measurements in the terminal portion of the internal carotid or proximal portion of the middle cerebral artery.^{11,12}

Cranial complications occur in at least 25% of patients with SCD. These complications include transient ischemic attacks, overt and silent cerebral infarction, cerebral hemorrhage, infections, moyamoya pattern, posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome, dural venous sinus thrombosis, thickness of the diploic space, and cerebral atrophy.^{2,13-15} The present study found a lower percentage of patients who developed neurological symptoms, most likely because of early SCD diagnosis, proper follow-up, and introducing hydroxyurea treatment at the appropriate time.

Some neurological features, such as headache or fatigue, are common in children with SCD and may overlap with the symptoms of other conditions, making it challenging to distinguish between sickle cell-related complications and other causes. Lastly, cognitive deficits in children with SCD may not be readily apparent, and standardized cognitive assessments may not be routinely performed, leading to a delay in diagnosis and management.

A multidisciplinary approach is required to address these challenges. Close collaboration among hematologists, neurologists, and other health care providers is crucial to promptly detect and manage neurological manifestations in children with SCD. Improved awareness and education regarding the potential for neurological complications in children with SCD, as well as access to specialized resources and diagnostic tools, is also essential for improving the detection and management of disease-related complications.

Study Strengths

This is the first study in the Eastern province that includes the Arab-Indian haplotype of SCD; it provides insight into the natural history of neurological complications in children with SCD, especially in the eastern region of Saudi Arabia. It

also covers many patients followed up over a long period.

Furthermore, we studied different clinical outcomes of SCD, as we collected data on factors such as patient demographics and treatment history, the risk factors for these complications, prevention, and management.

Study Limitations

A limitation of this study is that it was retrospective, and all data were collected from hospital medical records. Therefore, important information may have been omitted or not documented, and patients who did not report their symptoms may have been missed. Therefore, validation of our results with prospective studies is needed.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to improve early detection, prevention, and management of neurological complications in pediatric SCD:

1. Routine Neuroimaging
 - Annual MRI/MRA screening should be considered for children with abnormal TCD velocities, frequent headaches, or learning difficulties.
 - Early screening is especially crucial for detecting silent cerebral infarcts and moyamoya disease.
2. Strengthening TCD Programs
 - Ensure consistent TCD screening starting at age 2 years.
 - Automate recall systems to prevent missed appointments in high-risk patients.
3. Early Use of Disease-Modifying Therapy
 - Encourage early initiation of hydroxyurea in all eligible children.
 - Consider rapid escalation of therapy for those with low HbF levels.
4. Exchange Transfusion Protocols
 - Implement standardized clinical pathways for high-risk stroke patients.
 - Use exchange transfusion as first-line therapy for abnormal TCD or prior stroke.
5. Specialized Management of Moyamoya Disease
 - Establish referral pathways to neurosurgical centers for timely evaluation.
 - Consider early revascularization procedures when appropriate.
6. Neurocognitive Assessments
 - Implement periodic cognitive screening to detect learning difficulties early.
 - Coordinate with school-based services to provide academic support.
7. Multidisciplinary SCD Neurology Clinics
 - Integrate care between hematology, neurology, psychology, radiology, and rehabilitation.

- Improve family education on warning signs of neurological deterioration.

CONCLUSION:

A lower percentage of patients in our study had neurological symptoms, likely because of early SCD diagnosis, proper follow-up, and the use of hydroxyurea. Early detection and management of neurological complications are critical to minimizing their impact on affected children. Monitoring patients with SCD for signs of neurological dysfunction, including cognitive deficits and stroke, is crucial to prevent further deterioration and improve clinical outcomes.

Ethics Approval

The Medical Research and Ethics Committee of Qatif Health Network, Eastern Province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, approved this study (approval number: QCH-SREC0 20/2022).

Acknowledgments

We sincerely appreciate everyone who contributed to the success of this research, particularly, Haematology Unit at Qatif central hospital, Dr. Ahmad AlKhalifah and Dr. Ali Alkhabbaz.

Funding

None.

Conflicts of Interest

None declared.

Disclosure of AI Use:

Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies, were not utilized to support the preparation of this manuscript.

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